

Potenza Earthquake (18/3/2025)

The 2025 Potenza Earthquake

The **Mw 4.0 Potenza earthquake** occurred on **March 18, 2025**, at 09.01 UTC (10.01 Local Time). It is located nearby the city of Potenza, an area characterized by a complex tectonics, with normal faults striking in the Apennine direction and sitting above deeper strike-slip EW structures (main structures are depicted in the Figure with the seismicity of the area, monitored by ISNet).

Seismotectonic context

The **Mw 4.0 earthquake** occurred along the **Southern Apennines chain**, a fold and thrust belt characterized by ENE-verging duplexes geometries and out-of-sequence thrusting due to orogenic contraction. During the Quaternary the Southern Apennines thrust belt was

dissected by NW-SE oriented normal faults that accommodated an **extensional tectonic phase**, according to a stress field with the axis of maximum extension coaxial to the axis of maximum compression of Apennines belt (*Dogliani 1995; Patacca et Scandone, 2007a, Ascione, 2013*).

Historical earthquakes

Several earthquakes struck the Irpinia region with MCS intensity $I \geq X$, occurred in A.D. 989, 1694, 1930, and 1962 (*CPTI Working Group, 2019; Ascione et al., 2013*). The most destructive instrumental event was the **M_s 6.9, 1980 Irpinia earthquake** (*Bernard and Zollo, 1989*). The region also experienced a **M_w 5.7 strike slip event** in the area of Potenza in 1990. In the figure the seismicity and the focal mechanisms of the main last decade earthquakes are reported, with the location of the Potenza earthquake.

Seismic waveforms

Example of **seismic waveforms (vertical component)** recorded at the stations of ISNet, for the Mw 3.9 event in the epicentral distance range **5- 70 km**.

Absolute locations

We performed the absolute location of the Potenza event (yellow star) with NLLoc (*Lomax, 2009*) and the 1D P- and S-wave models optimized for the area (*Matrullo et al., 2011*). For improving the azimuthal coverage, we integrated the INFO network with **10 RAN stations** (network IT, blue triangles) and **2 INGV stations** (network IV, red triangles). The location is constrained with **56 arrival times (28 P and 28 S)**, GAP 149°, and horizontal and vertical location errors of 300 m and 200 m, respectively.

Foreshocks and Aftershocks

Other two events occurred last week in the area: one before the Mw 4.0 Potenza event on 14/03/2025 at 12:26 (Mw 2.3, yellow star) and another 38 minutes later at 09:38 (Mw 2.2, red star). We integrated ISNet (blue triangles), INGV, and RAN data (light blue triangles) and located events using NLLoc in the 3D velocity models by *De Landro et al. (2022)*. Locations are well constrained, with $RMS \leq 0.2$ s and errors of 300 m (Potenza) and 700 m (smaller events). Seismic events from 2018–2023 are also shown (dots in grayscale by depth). The three events align NW-SE, consistent with the Mw 4.0 event's focal mechanism strike. Section AA', perpendicular to the strike, confirms alignment with the Mw 4.0 event's focal mechanism dip.

Source parameters

We computed source parameters from spectral modelling of waveforms (*Supino et al., 2019*) using **17 stations**, integrating the accelerometers of the Rete Accelerometrica Nazionale

(RAN) with data from ISNet. The resulting average moment magnitude is **Mw 4.0±0.1**. Source radius has been estimated to be **620±30 m**, using the model *Kaneko & Shearer (2014)*. This resulted in a stress drop of **2.2±0.2 MPa**.

LPdT (Logarithm of P-wave peak displacement vs. time) curves

We computed the Logarithm of P-wave peak Displacement vs. Time after double integration of acceleration waveforms within 25 km hypocentral distance from the closest station to event hypocenter (PGN), starting from the P-wave arrival time. We built the single station and event-average LPdT curves (*Colombelli et al. 2014*). Single station curves show a clear dependency with distance in their plateau level, which is assumed to be a proxy for the earthquake magnitude. Following the approach of *Longobardi et al. 2025* we used the event-average LPdT curve to estimate: **the half of the plateau level time (tHALF)** and **the initial slope of the LPdT curve (up to tHALF)** to compute the moment magnitude, using empirical scaling relationships previously calibrated. We found a moment magnitude estimate **Mw_SLOPE= 4.0 ± 0.2** from the initial slope and **Mw_THALF= 4.1 ± 0.2** from the time parameter.

Focal mechanism from polarities

From the retrieved absolute location, we estimated the focal mechanism using FPFIT (*Reasenberg & Oppenheimer, 1986*) inverting **18 P-wave polarities from INFO, INGV and RAN stations**. The retrieved fault plane reports **pure normal faulting mechanism**, whose angles are coherent with the orientation of the extensional regional stress field and with the geometrical characteristics of the main structures of the area.

M < 5.5, only one point source
STF not constrained hence not shown

Best fit slip rake
130.0 30.0 -104.5 : best focal mechanism
RMSC = 0.640
Selected depth: 12.0 km
20 = number of components
79 % : rate of confidence
4.21 : Max from waveform inversion
Epicenter used (lat, long): 40.678 15.855
Slipping direction: N
strike dip rake of the second nodal plane:
305.6 51.0 81.8
----- quality B -----
*** Signification of quality ***
A: local mechanism STRONGLY CONSTRAINED
B: local mechanism WELL CONSTRAINED
C: local mechanism MODERATELY CONSTRAINED
D: local mechanism WEAKLY CONSTRAINED
E: local mechanism BARELY CONSTRAINED
F: local mechanism NOT CONSTRAINED
Event directory:
ipernat_SentSouls/MWF/FMNEAR_global/FMNEAR/20250318090126_2
Date of computation:
Tue Mar 18 10:22:47 CET 2025
Method used: FMNEAR
!!! AUTOMATIC COMPUTATION !!!

Focal Mechanism from Moment Tensor

The moment tensor was also calculated using FMNEAR (*Delouis, 2014*) using full-waveform modelling at 9 stations. The solution demonstrates a pure normal fault mechanism analogous to the one retrieved from polarities, with depth comparable with location. Selected plane is 130, 30, -105 for strike, dip and rake.

Focal mechanism by inversion of P polarities, and P- and S- amplitudes

Focal mechanism by inversion of P-polarity, and P- and S-amplitudes (*Tarantino et al., 2024*) using the traces of the Isnet network and the location from the ISNet bulletin. The solution was generated shortly after the event by the experimental automatic numerical procedures running in background on the earthquakes of the Isnet catalog and managed by the RISSC lab. Despite the limited number of observations, the solutions show a nearly pure normal faulting in line with the mechanisms found by the other methods with richer datasets.

Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS)

The event was recorded by a **DAS** instrument that interrogates a **20km long telecommunication cable**, monitoring the southern part of the ISNet network. Following the methodology proposed in *Trabattoni et al. (2023)* we converted the data to displacement and used the local law (*Bobbio et al., 2009*) to estimate local magnitude along the cable from Wood-Anderson equivalent displacement traces. We find a final median estimate of **ML 3.8 +/- 0.2** that is coherent with observations from standard stations in the network.

Ground Motion - PGV

We performed a **ground motion analysis** at the **ISNet**, **INGV** and **RAN** stations that have recorded the event. The **average epicentral distance** of the **ISNet** stations is **42.9 km** with a minimum distance of **12.8 km** (station **IX.PGN3** - Pignola PZ) and a maximum of **80.4 km** (**IX.LGS3** - Luogosano AV). The closest station of the **RAN** network was **IT.PTZ** (**5.2 km of epicentral distance**)

The **maximum PGV at ISNet** was recorded at the station **IX.BEL3** (Bella PZ - **epicentral distance 18.9 km**) with a value of **0.22 cm/s**.

The **minimum PGV at ISNet** was recorded at the station **IX.MNT3** (Montella AV - **epicentral distance 73.6 km**) with a value of **0.01 cm/s**.

The **maximum absolute PGV** was recorded at the station **IX.POT7** (**epicentral distance 5.6 km**) with a value of **1.46 cm/s**.

The **observed PGV** values are overall compatible with the expected ones from an **the attenuation law** proposed by *Bindi et al. (2011)*, commonly used for crustal Italian events). However, **several stations** experienced a **larger than expected shaking**, mostly southeastward from the epicenter. Comparing this result with the focal mechanism solution, this can be due to an **along-strike directive effect**.

The shaking map is computed interpolating **the observations** with the **attenuation law** proposed by *Bindi et al. (2011)* through the use of the software **ShakeMap**.

Ground Motion - PGA

At the same stations we here show the results for the Peak Ground Acceleration (**PGA**). We retrieved a maximum value at ISNet of **0.8%g** at the station **IX.PGN3** and the minimum value at (**0.02%g**) at the farthest station **IX.LGS3**. The **maximum absolute PGA** was recorded at station **IT.POT7** with a value of **4.9%g**

The **observed values** are overall **compatible** with the **ones predicted** by the attenuation law proposed by *Bindi et al. (2011)*. Similarly to PGV, several stations **several stations** experienced a **larger than expected acceleration**, mostly southeastward from the epicenter.

The **shaking map** is computed interpolating the **observations** with the **attenuation law** proposed by *Bindi et al. (2011)* through the use of the software **ShakeMap**

Ground Motion - Macroseismic Intensity

Finally the **observed PGV** and **PGA** are converted into Macroseismic Intensity (**MMI**) values through the relation proposed by *Faenza and Michelini (2012)*. The **maximum MMI** at ISNet were found at the stations **IX.BEL3** and **IX.PGN3**. At these stations a **MMI=IV** was retrieved, corresponding to **LIGHT** shaking and **NONE** damage. The strongest absolute intensity was estimated at **IT.POT7** with a value **MMI=VI** corresponding to **STRONG** shaking and potential **LIGHT** damage.

Earthquake Early Warning Testing

PRESTo Early Warning System (source-based)

Final screenshot while processing the earthquake. Real-time alerts are sent to target sites: location, magnitude, expected PGAs and lead-times. **Final magnitude (ML)** has been estimated to **3.5**.

First alert at OT + 8.0s (3.1s from 1st pick, 5 stations): ΔM -0.3, ΔEPI 11.1 km, ΔDEP 14.3 km

Stable alerts from OT + 14.4s (9.7s from 1st pick, 13 stations): ΔM -0.7, ΔEPI 8.8 km, ΔDEP 6.3 km

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Il sistema di Early Warning PRESTo, in fase di sperimentazione presso il RISSC-Lab,
ha rilevato automaticamente un evento:

ML: 3.5
Data: 2025-03-18 09:01:26.54 (UTC)
Località: Potenza (PZ)
Google Map

utilizzando 15 stazioni della rete ISNet - Irpinia Seismic Network.
La prima informazione su magnitudo e localizzazione dell'evento è stata disponibile al tempo:
2025-03-18 09:01:33.84 (UTC)

Cioè circa 4.8 secondi dopo il primo arrivo P rilevato alla stazione PGN3 al tempo:
2025-03-18 09:01:28.99 (UTC)

In allegato il rapporto dettagliato e l'istantanea.

Per una completa statistica degli eventi rilevati da PRESTo nella fase di sperimentazione,
consultare il bollettino on-line.
  
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PRESTo message

Automatic email message from PRESTo based on the final stable estimates was actually received by RISSC-Lab members. **This was sent at OT + 24s** (15s from the start of the processing of the earthquake).

PRESTo Timeline

Time evolution of PRESTo source parameters estimates (location, magnitude) compared to the manually revised values from the INGV bulletin. The number of available stations vs. time from OT is shown in the graph at the bottom. The large difference in location and depth with the Bulletin estimate is due to uncertainties related to the occurrence of the event at the border of the network.

PRESTo Data Transmission Latency

Time delays from the ground motion data acquisition at each station to PRESTo processing. Thanks to fast telemetry and short packet sizes from the data-loggers, **data is received within 1 second** for almost all working stations, allowing for prompt alerts.

QuakeUp Early Warning system (impact-based)

Final screenshot while processing the earthquake in simulation mode (off-line playback of the real waveforms). In real-time mode alerts would be sent to target sites: location, magnitude, expected PGAs and lead-times. **Final magnitude (ML)** has been estimated to **3.8**.

First alert at OT + 7s (4.5s from 1st pick, 4 stations): ΔM -0.8, ΔEPI 20 km, ΔDEP 10.4 km

Stable alerts from OT + 14.4s (11.9s from 1st pick, 13 stations): ΔM -0.3, ΔEPI 9 km, ΔDEP 3 km

QuakeUp Early Warning system (impact-based) - Source parameters estimations

Evolution in time (as seconds from O.T.) of the estimations provided by the shaking-forecast EWS (QuakeUp) (Zollo et al., 2023; Rea et al., 2024). The location errors in the top panel are calculated as the distance from the reference location (ISNet bulletin). The large error in location is related to location of the event at the border of the network.

The lower panel shows the evolution in time of the average ML estimation (blue dotted line) and the single-station estimations (gray lines). The final average local magnitude value is 3.8.

Real-time performance of the on-site Early warning system SAVE at PGN3 station.

The figure shows the screenshot of SAVE at the closest ISNet recording station (PGN3 - distance of 12.8 km). All the estimates are obtained using the first 3 seconds of recorded P-wave signal. The **estimated intensity** (through the Pd) **was IV**, and the **observed intensity** (through PGV) **was IV**. The magnitude of the event was classified as "Moderate" ($3 < M < 5$) and the event was estimated to be "Near" the recording stations (ie., at hypocentral distance smaller than 50km). The magnitude is also estimated using the Tauc parameters ($M_w = 4.7$) and the parameter $P_d \times T_{auc}$ ($M_w 3.6$)

Intensity Predictions from the offline playback of the on-site Early warning system SAVE at all stations.

The figure shows the results that would have been obtained from the on-site Early warning system SAVE, with independent running at all stations of the network. The map on the left shows the intensities that would have been predicted within 3 seconds from the P-wave arrival while the right-side plot shows the comparison between the predicted and observed PGV values. The figure shows a systematic overestimation of the observed intensity, that can be attributed to the used empirical relation between the PGV and P-peak amplitude not calibrated for the Irpinia region.

SismUp - EEW App

The images show the performance of the EEW app for mobile smartphones. The first estimate was calculated based on the data received from the alert (e.g. magnitude, epicenter latitude, epicenter longitude). Last estimate was calculated based on the data from the latest update of the seismic event generated by PRESTo and using the location of the smartphone at the time of the alert.

ULTIMA STIMA

PRIMA STIMA

Tempo origine ora locale

18-03-2025 10:01:24

Tempo origine UTC

18-03-2025 09:01:24

Magnitudo	ML 3.9
Latitudine Epicentro	40.6289
Longitudine Epicentro	15.9701
Profondità	0 Km
Distanza dall'epicentro	148 Km

Tempo origine ora locale

18-03-2025 10:01:24

Tempo origine UTC

18-03-2025 09:01:24

Magnitudo	ML 3.5
Latitudine Epicentro	40.6344
Longitudine Epicentro	15.7666
Profondità	8 Km
Distanza dall'epicentro	131 Km

SismUp - EEW App

4 smartphones received the PRESTo alert for this event. The smartphones were located at: Naples, Perugia, Sevilla. The smartphones received the warning within an average time of 1 s

Summary

Potenza Earthquake (18/03/2025):

- **Date and Time:** Occurred on March 18, 2025, at 09:01 UTC (10:01 local time).
- **Magnitude:** Moment magnitude (M_w) 4.0.
- **Location:** Near Potenza city, Southern Apennines, Italy, in a region with complex tectonics involving normal and strike-slip faults.
- **Seismotectonic & Historical Context:** Occurred within the Southern Apennines fold and thrust belt, dominated by extensional tectonics characterized by NW-SE normal faults. Region previously affected by severe earthquakes, notably the devastating M_s 6.9 Irpinia earthquake (1980) and a M_w 5.7 event near Potenza (1990).
- **Event Size and Stress Drop:** Fault rupture approximately 1.2 km in size; stress drop estimated at 2.2 MPa.
- **Focal Mechanism:** Pure normal faulting, consistent with regional tectonic stress and geometry. Moment tensor solution: strike 130° , dip 30° , rake -105° .
- **Seismicity:** Accompanied by smaller seismic events (M_L 2.1 and M_L 1.8) occurring closely in time and aligned along the NW-SE direction.
- **Ground Motion Analysis:**

- **Peak Ground Velocity (PGV):** Maximum observed PGV 1.46 cm/s at station IX.POT7 (5.6 km epicentral distance).
- **Peak Ground Acceleration (PGA):** Maximum observed PGA 4.9%g at station IT.POT7.
- **Macroseismic Intensity (MMI):** Highest intensity (VI) at IT.POT7, indicating strong shaking and potential for light damage. Generally light (MMI IV) elsewhere.
- **Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS):** Successfully recorded event providing coherent ML=3.8 estimates.
- **Early Warning Systems (EWS):**
 - **PRESTo (source-based)** issued first alert ~8.8 s after origin time; stable magnitude estimates within ~15 s.
 - **QuakeUp (impact-based)** issued first alert ~7 s after origin time; provided accurate shaking estimates.
 - **SAVE (on-site system)** accurately estimated intensity and magnitude at closest stations, slightly overestimated intensities across the network.
 - **SismUp App:** EEW smartphone application successfully transmitted alerts within ~1 s to users in multiple locations (Naples, Perugia, Sevilla).
- **Automatic real-time systems:** Provided reliable real-time information about location, local and moment magnitude, ground shaking. Early warning correctly issued by regional and onsite systems.

Contributors

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Useful links

Irpinia Seismic Network¹

Seismic Bulletin of ISNet²

CREW - EEW Testing Centre³

¹<https://isnet.unina.it>

²<http://isnet-bulletin.fisica.unina.it/cgi-bin/isnet-events/isnet.cgi>

